

Is globalisation leading to the ‘end of geography’?

Globalisation is the spread of resources and promotion of global interconnectedness. Globalisation is not the ‘end of geography’, but rather causes changes in geography. The predicted ‘end of geography’, or ‘borderless world’ supposedly caused by globalisation, is a homogenous world, where everyone and everything everywhere are equal; in circumstance, in opportunity, and in life. That is the point at which geography ends. Consequently, in this essay I will argue that this point has not been reached, with evidence in the Electric Vehicle (EV) industry’s production process, legislation, and trade connections. The reason something as new and niche as the EV industry can be evaluated under a geographical lens, is that it is an increasingly important commodity in its production and geopolitics. Many countries, thanks to the Paris Climate Agreement, have accepted new renewable energy, to meet net-zero goals. This forces the most energy consuming sector of transportation to make changes, giving EVs a strong future in the global economy.

The battery of an electric vehicle is the most important part of the car and consequently makes up most of the cost of production (Eddy *et al.* 2019). The resources used to produce the battery are mainly metals, the rarest being graphite, lithium, and cobalt; less rare, but nonetheless necessary, are copper, nickel, manganese, aluminium, and steel (Perry 2022). Graphite is mined and produced mainly by China, with 65% of natural graphite and 45% of synthetic graphite produced there, and firms processing 95% into useable battery-ready graphite (Ballinger *et al.* 2019). Additionally, 91% of lithium production is completed by the combined efforts of Australia, Argentina, and Chile (Ballinger *et al.* 2019). Ballinger *et al.* (2019) also explains that 90% of cobalt is by-product from nickel or copper mining, and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is responsible for 50% of cobalt production. Just three of the necessary metals in EV batteries are located across 4 continents. With this many locations involved, it is far from an ‘end of geography’. Additionally, China has an increasing grip on other areas of mining. Half of copper and cobalt mining operations are Chinese-owned, and further yet, cobalt refining is mainly performed in China (Rajaeifar *et al.* 2022). The International Energy Agency (IEA) (2022) claims that Europe is home to 20% of copper refining, and is responsible for $\frac{1}{4}$ of global EV production, however $\frac{3}{4}$ of all lithium batteries will have been made in China. On the other hand, because China owns so much of the supply chain for EV batteries, see Figure 1, it could be argued that globalisation is causing an ‘end of geography’ in the unified location of battery production. However, battery production is globally limited and is not regarded as equal opportunity throughout the supply chain. Geography lives on. Many future projects will follow this pattern, with 46 of 70 announced

Figure 1: Location of EV battery production. Source: IEA (2022)

gigafactories for EV battery production located in China (Eddy *et al.* 2019). However, there are also new resource deposits being discovered and attracting investment; like the nickel belt in east Africa, consequently starting a project in Tanzania, or lithium in Bolivia (IEA 2022). The IEA (2022) also explores how Volkswagen and others plan on building facilities in Europe and the US for cathode production, which would further diversify the supply chain. The battery of an EV could involve contributions of more than 10 countries before being placed inside a car to be sold, or just China. However, the parts add up to an unmistakable conclusion; a battery cannot be made purely in, say, Germany, and since it can in China, this isn't a homogenized world, because Germany and China are not equals in resource opportunity.

Yet another inequality is in the geopolitics of EV batteries and their cars. In a world without geography, tariffs, and trade agreements, do not exist because the world is homogenised and therefore borderless. Since China owns the majority of the global EV market, it is no surprise that government funding for such an advantage began decades ago, with the 'Catalogue for Guiding Industry Restructuring (2007 Version)' (Nieuwenhuis and Wells 2015). Being the first piece of legislation to include a directive on the management of EV related projects, it wasn't until 2009 that the 'Automobile Industry Restructuring and Revitalisation Plan' was approved and implemented (Nieuwenhuis and Wells 2015). In 2022 the IEA notes that Korea and Japan, at 5% and 4% of EV supply chain respectively, also began legislation endorsement, and promotion of EV battery production years ago. Meanwhile, countries like the US, Canada, the EU, India, Thailand, and Indonesia, are only just beginning to venture into supporting their own EV markets (IEA 2022). The US, which holds 7% of EV Battery Production (EVBP), started with an executive order to investigate

the risks of high-capacity batteries (IEA 2022). This kick-started many new government projects, like funding to take more carbon off roads, increase battery production facilities, including mining, refining, and assembly processes (IEA 2022). The IEA (2022) includes that Canada; at 0% EVBP, implemented a government package to install more battery assembly facilities, including the largest of its kind in Ontario. At the ‘end of geography’ a region like Canada and the US would share similar resources and yet the US holds 7% EVBP while Canada holds nil. If not for a lack of resources, then for a lack of government advocacy, which continues to contradict the fully globalised ‘end of geography’ ideal of total equality. India, which also currently holds 0% of EVBP, is making headway with a ‘Production Linked Incentives scheme’, working to award 5-year subsidies to private recipients which show entrepreneurship through improvement in battery performance (IEA 2022). In comparison with Indonesia, adding up to 1% EVBP with Thailand, government funding supports domestically sourced components through state-owned manufacturers (IEA 2022). Though similar in their goals, these two countries adopt quite different tactics, seen in the levels of government intervention. All these countries held varying, but different responses in time taken, and in support given to the EV market, before eventually assimilating the ideas into an established economy.

A particular instance of differing responses from countries’ governments, is the issue of Brexit, and how it will affect the EV market in Europe. Due to their recent withdrawal from the European Union (EU), the United Kingdom (UK) is facing economic backlash in the form of tariffs. More specifically those on EV production, which will be formerly implemented on January 1, 2024, unless the European Automobile Manufacturers Association (ACEA) and the European Commission can come to an agreement on taxation of EVs traded between the UK and the EU (ACEA 2023). Under current, ‘rules of origin’, a 10% tariff will be levied onto European EV exports, unless much of the battery’s material and parts are sourced from the UK or the EU, and, as previously mentioned, Europe holds very little of the supply chain for EV batteries. Another more recent development in the US saw President Biden sign regulations which severely limit tax credits available on EVs imported from China (Bikales 2023). In both the UK/EU and US/China instances, the two regions are competing for the market and subsequent profit. In a ‘borderless world’, one in which geography doesn’t exist, tariffs on imported goods would not exist, the idea of these countries, or collation of countries, existing as separate entities in an economical sense would be false, or would at least be true in this world where geography remains.

The 'end of geography', something yet to prevail in the global economy, would be fully equal in resources and governments, and borderless in trade. Despite this, the world is, and will continue to be interconnected, through resource demands, legislation and trade agreements and disagreements. Geography is still a long way from coming to an end.

Reference List

- ACEA - European Automobile Manufacturers' Association. (2023). *EU-UK Battery rules: Act Now and Do the Right thing, EU Auto Chief Urges Commission*. [online] Available at: <https://www.acea.auto/press-release/eu-uk-battery-rules-act-now-and-do-the-right-thing-eu-auto-chief-urges-commission/> [Accessed 1 Dec. 2023].
- Ballinger, B., Stringer, M., Schmeda-Lopez, D.R., Kefford, B., Parkinson, B., Greig, C. and Smart, S. (2019). The Vulnerability of Electric Vehicle Deployment to Critical Mineral Supply. *Applied Energy*, [online] 255(1), p.113844. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113844>.
- Bikales, J. (2023). *POLITICO Pro*. [online] subscriber.politicopro.com. Available at: <https://subscriber.politicopro.com/article/2023/12/bidens-latest-china-crackdown-puts-his-ev-ambitions-at-risk-00129475> [Accessed 1 Dec. 2023].
- Eddy, J., Pfeiffer, A. and Van De Staij, J. (2019). *Recharging economies: the EV-battery manufac- Turing Outlook for Europe as Uptake of Electric Vehicles (EVs) increases, the EV-battery Market Represents an Opportunity for European players. We Assess the po- Tential and Look at Factors Guiding the Location of Production Capacity*. [online] Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Industries/Oil%20and%20Gas/Our%20Insights/Recharging%20economies%20The%20EV%20battery%20manufacturing%20outlook%20for%20Europe/Recharging-economies-The-EV-battery-manufacturing-outlook-for-Europe-vF.pdf> [Accessed 1 Dec. 2023].
- International Energy Agency (2022). *Global Supply Chains of EV Batteries*. [online] Available at: <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/4eb8c252-76b1-4710-8f5e-867e751c8dda/GlobalSupplyChainsOfEVBatteries.pdf> [Accessed 1 Dec. 2023].
- Nieuwenhuis, P. and Wells, P. (2015). *The Global Automotive Industry*. 1st ed. [online] *ebookcentral.proquest.com*. John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated. Available at: <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/rhul/reader.action?docID=4038798&ppg=210&query=%26quot> [Accessed 1 Dec. 2023].
- Perry, T. (2019). *How Electric Car Batteries Are Made: from Mining to Driving*. [online] Green Car Future. Available at: <https://www.greencarfuture.com/electric/making-of-ev-batteries> [Accessed 1 Dec. 2023].
- Rajaeifar, M.A., Ghadimi, P., Raugei, M., Wu, Y. and Heidrich, O. (2022). Challenges and Recent Developments in Supply and Value Chains of Electric Vehicle batteries: a

Sustainability Perspective. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, [online] 180(106144), p.106144. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.106144>.